

Test entries were planted in two rows of 10 hills each, alternated with a skip row of susceptible check TN1. Closer spacing (15 × 10 cm) and a topdressing of extra N above the recommended dose were used to induce higher BPH incidence in the trials. We scored entries in the field during peak BPH incidence and when TN1 died.

Promising entries that recorded BPH damage score of 2-3 were BPT2217, BPT4363, BPT4365, RP2332-19-9-6, RP2362-227-22, RP2542-1657-194, RP2543-1444-46, RP2543-1464-152, local check ADT36, and local resistant check PY3 (see table). RP1746-1723-8, RP2332-16-3, and RP2332-18-15 were resistant to BPH (score 3), but susceptible to leafhopper. □

Sources of resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) in rice

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We studied 108 rice cultivars to identify sources of resistance to the local biotype of BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) under laboratory conditions using the bulk seedling test.

Test entries were sown in 20-cm rows, 5 cm apart, in 60- × 45- × 10-cm wooden boxes at Rice Research Station, Moncompu, Kerala, from 1985 to 1988. Each box contained 24 lines including four of susceptible check TN1 and two of resistant check PTB33.

Seedlings were thinned to 20 per row at 7 d. Seedboxes were placed inside 70- × 55- × 15-cm trays with 5 cm of water in them. Trays were kept inside a screening cage. After 1 wk each seedling was infested with an average of five second-instar BPH nymphs. Damage was scored by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) scale when about 90% of TN1 had died. Screening was repeated three times.

Forty rice cultivars were resistant (see table), 22 moderately resistant, 13 moderately susceptible, and 33 highly susceptible. Resistant entries were of diverse origin: Indonesia (1), Sri Lanka (3), Philippines (7), and India (29). Of the Indian types, 13 (and PTB33) were from Kerala. □

Resistant entries and BPH score.^a

Designation	Origin	Damage score (0-9)	Designation	Origin	Damage score (0-9)
Sinna Sivappu	Sri Lanka	2.9	RP1015-45-114-1	India	1.8
Lekham Samba	Sri Lanka	2.6	KAU1734-2 ^b	India	2.9
Kuru Hondarawala	Sri Lanka	1.2	RP1015-100-25-4	India	2.7
IR40	Philippines	2.4	KAU2084 ^b	India	1.2
IR25984-92-1-3	Philippines	2.5	KAU169 ^b	India	2.7
IR1552	Philippines	1.2	KAU126 ^b	India	2.6
IR5741-73-2-3	Philippines	2.8	KAU153-1 ^b	India	1.6
IR22082-41-2	Philippines	2.1	KAU168 ^b	India	2.7
IR24	Philippines	2.5	KAU93 ^b	India	2.2
IR9830-26-3-3	Philippines	2.7	MO 4 ^b	India	2.8
CR266-407-4	India	1.2	MO 5 ^b	India	2.6
RP2695-5-7-32	India	1.5	MO 6 ^b	India	2.0
RP2068-32-2-2	India	1.6	MO 7 ^b	India	2.0
MTU5194	India	1.7	M102 ^b	India	2.9
RP2695-5-8-31	India	1.9	RP1015-15-7-7-2	India	2.9
MTU5295	India	1.7	RP1579-73-1864	India	2.8
RP2068-17-2-2	India	1.6	RP1579-1863-73-32-53	India	2.8
RP1579-56-1907	India	1.6	ARC6650	India	2.9
RP1756-39	India	1.4	M66-B-45-1	Indonesia	1.8
TNAU BPHR8275	India	2.4	PTB33 (resistant check) ^b	India	2.4
MTU4870	India	1.6	TN1 (susceptible check)	Taiwan	8.7

^aScored by SES. All entries except TN1 were resistant. ^bFrom Kerala.

Virulence of a new biotype of brown planthopper (BPH) in Mekong Delta

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Six BPH populations from five ecological areas in the Mekong Delta were collected to determine their virulence on rice using the modified bulk seedling test.

Differential check varieties were seeded in 20-cm rows, 5 cm apart, in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes with three replications. Test varieties were infested 7 d after seeding with 5-8 second- and third-instar nymphs per seedling. Damage was visually rated using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1-9) when the susceptible check TN1 had died.

All new biotype populations killed TN1. Mudgo (*Bph 1*) was moderately

Reaction^a of BPH on differential check varieties, Mekong Delta, 1990-91.

Site, season	Host of BPH population	BPH score ^a on					
		TN1 (none)	Mudgo (<i>Bph 1</i>)	ASD7 (<i>bph 2</i>)	Rathu Heenati (<i>Bph 3</i>)	PTB33 (digenic)	Babawee (<i>bph 4</i>)
Angiang	IR64	9	7	9	3	3	3
1990 WS		9	7	7	3	0	3
1991 DS	MTL 85	9	7	7	0	1	5
Angiang		9	5	9	5	0	3
1990 WS	MTL 85	9	5	7	5	0	5
1991 DS		9	5	9	5	0	5
Tiengiang	OM59-7	9	5	7	3	1	1
1990 WS		9	5	9	3	1	5
1991 DS	IR42	9	3	7	1	0	7
Haugiang		9	3	7	1	0	7
1990 WS	IR19660	9	7	9	5	0	5
1991 DS		9	7	9	5	0	5

^aAv of 3 replications. By the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale.

susceptible or susceptible to new BPH populations, except the Minh hai population. The resistance of ASD7 (*bph* 2) broke down in Mekong Delta, indicating that biotype 2 BPH had developed a new, distinct biotype. Rathu Heenati (*Bph* 3) was particularly resistant to Angiang, Haugiang, and Minh hai populations, but moderately susceptible to those of Tiengiang and Cuulong. PTB33 (digenic gene) was still resistant to all populations. Babawee (*bph* 4) was moderately susceptible to the new BPH biotype.

BPH virulence in Mekong Delta is becoming higher than that of biotype 2 because of natural adaptive selections. Reactions of different populations in various areas were not similar; therefore they were geographically biotypes of BPH somewhere in Mekong Delta. □

Yield losses due to stalk-eyed fly (SEF) in Nigeria

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Heavy infestation (deadheart) of SEF *Diopsis longicornis* Macquart is observed every year at the IITA experimental farm in Nigeria. This infestation precedes the off-season when SEF adults emerge from weeds to colonize early transplanted rice.

We studied yield losses caused by SEF in early 1989 wet season (WS) in four irrigated lowland rices: FARO 8 (MAS), ITA306, TN1, and IR20. Grain yields from single hills were compared.

SEF damage was at its peak 2 wk after transplanting. Infested and healthy hills were randomly selected, tagged, SEF damage (% per hill) assessed, and grain yields (at maturity) recorded. Hills were monitored weekly for pests other than SEF, but none attained threshold level.

Damaged tillers from each hill were categorized (see table). Hills with an equal number of productive tillers were selected from both infested and healthy

Effect of SEF damage on grain yields of 4 lowland irrigated rices.^a IITA, Nigeria, 1989 wet season.

Rice variety	Total hills (no.)	Grain yield (g/hill, $\bar{X} \pm$ SD)					Yield loss/hill (g)
		Infested tillers				Healthy hill	
		1–20%	21–40%	≥41	<60%		
FARO 8 (MAS)	56	30.2 ± 16.7 (57)	23.3 ± 13.0 (43)	– (0)	27.0 ± 14.9	35.8 ± 19.0	8.8
ITA306	276	17.1 ± 7.8 (54)	14.9 ± 11.0 (41)	22.0 ± 10.0 (5)	18.0 ± 9.6	18.1 ± 10.0	0.1
TN1	76	17.7 ± 9.0 (68)	11.6 ± 9.0 (29)	10.0 ± 0.0 (3)	13.1 ± 6.0	16.0 ± 7.0	2.9
IR20	124	18.3 ± 12.5 (44)	12.0 ± 8.8 (50)	6.7 ± 3.6 (6)	12.3 ± 8.3	21.6 ± 7.0	9.3

^aValues in parentheses indicate hills infested (%) in that category.

hills to minimize differences in yield potential.

The largest percentage of hills showed 1–20% damage (except those of IR20). Yield losses to SEF varied among varieties and damage varied within categories (except in ITA306).

Grain weight declined with increased SEF damage in all rice varieties except ITA306 (see table). This confirmed our field observation that SEF-damaged ITA306 plants recover from infestation; we could not detect yield losses at this damage level. □

Stress tolerance

A simple technique for mass screening of rice germplasm tolerant of photo-oxidation

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Photo-oxidation of chlorophyll is a physiological effect on rice under stress

conditions. We developed a simple technique to screen rice germplasm tolerant of photo-oxidation.

Eight mature rice leaves/plant were detached at different growth stages and submerged in a white tray filled with water containing 10–30 ppm CO₂ and 0.5–0.6% O₂ under sunlight at 30–35 °C for 5–7 d. A transparent glass bar covered the leaves to prevent floating.

Leaf color was graded at the end of treatment on a scale of 1–5 (see table). Photo-oxidation-tolerant varieties were

Grades^a of leaf color in various varieties at heading stage.

Varieties ^b				
Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3	Grade 4	Grade 5
Nan geng 35 (J)	BR 1083-4 1-2-4-2- 1 (I)	Nan nong da 4008 (I)	Jia nong xian yu 23 (I)	Milyang 23 (I)
02428 (J)	Hualienyu 124 (J)	3037 (I)	Taiyin1 (I)	IB29B (I)
729 (J)	Tngy 1 (J)	Pusa 33 (I)	Yanxuan 156 (I)	Nj 57161 (I)
020 (J)	Tian rui 408 (I)	C662083 (I)	Shan you 63 (I)	NJ 67022 (I)
Yayou 2 (J)	Niu jiaonuo (J)	Palghar 31-1-3 (I)	Nangeng 11A/CS7 (J)	Guicha 02 (I)
		IR44526-47-3-2 (I)	7901-TR16-1-1 (I)	IR58 (I)
		Ge 1868-5-4 (I)	E 164 (I)	Sixizhan (I)
		Ha 361 (I)	Shui tuan 287 (I)	Colombia (I)
		Zong yu 87-1 (I)	IRI346 (I)	Laijing (I)
		Tai nan sen 12 (I)	Della (I)	ITA222 (I)
		Min ke zao 6 (I)	Minyu 4399 (I)	
		CT6417-2-1-1-1p (I)	Zhong yu 4376 (I)	
		Nannong nuo4001 (I)	Yunxia 32 (I)	
		Let 9702 (I)	Nancarp A (I)	
		Sipi 681032 (I)	Bknlr-75091 (I)	
		Xiao jia nuo (I)	Jia nong xian yu 23 (I)	
		IR36 (I)	Min ke zao 1 (I)	
		Nj 701 35 (I)	Ai ma hang (I)	
		Xiang zhong sen 2 (I)	Leah (I)	
		Milyang 23 (I)		

^aGrades (scores) 1 = green, 2 = yellowish tip, 3 = yellowish 1/3, 4 = yellowish 1/2, 5 = yellowish whole leaf. ^bJ = japonica, I = indica.